

IS CRICKET JUMP PERFORMANCE DEPENDENT ON AGE/SIZE?

by

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Abstract

Crickets utilize elastically powered movements when jumping. They have a specific development where their age is directly proportional to their size, so the larger a cricket is, the older they are, and vice versa. Animals of the same species are expected to have similar shape and muscle proportion, despite their differences in size. Since the height of one's jump depends on the proportion of body mass to muscle mass, organisms of the same species are expected to jump the same height regardless of their differences in size. Therefore, older crickets are predicted to have better and more consistent jump performance compared to smaller crickets. To further understand potential factors that affect their jumps, the jumps of two different-sized crickets with five replicates in each size (a total of 10 crickets with 10 jumps from each cricket) were recorded using a high-speed camera. Each of the videos was then digitized and analyzed using a DLTdv8 and a MATLAB script to determine if their age/size affects their jump performance. It was found that older crickets jump at a higher velocity compared to younger crickets, however, there was no significant difference in the variances of their jumps. By understanding the differences in how the crickets of different ages/sizes jump, engineers could potentially make adjustments or modifications to better the control and performance of certain jumping creations, such as bionic robots.

Introduction

When animals are placed in dangerous situations, oftentimes, they can use either mechanical, chemical, physical, or behavioral defenses to escape. For example, one of the simplest ways an animal can escape from a dangerous situation is by jumping. Several animals use jumping as a means of escape, including grasshoppers, frogs, kangaroos, and much more (9). Animals need to move in a variety of situations that can impact their fitness, which is something that is not completely yet understood. It is important to understand how animals are adapted to their environment and the evolutionary forces that have led to their evolution. It is also important to realize that animals can do things that our machines cannot do as well compared to them. This study aims to determine potential factors that may influence jump performance in crickets. In doing so, we can better understand how to modify our robots to better engineer them, since consistency and accuracy are important in jumping robots, such as bionic robots (9).

Jumping is easy to understand in terms of physics, making it easier to engineer in robots. Although jumping may sound like the simplest form of prey defenses, developing a strong

understanding of it can be extremely useful in both biology and engineering. Jumping is also used in life-or-death situations, which probably represents high effort in organisms. For example, it is often used by animals to escape from dangerous situations, like an approaching predator (10). Avoiding predation is critical for survival and individual fitness. Therefore, natural selection may favor individuals of a species with higher jumping ability, regardless of body size (8). Most of the time, juveniles typically suffer higher predation rates compared to adults, making selection much stronger for juvenile escape performance. From an evolutionary perspective, organisms are likely to adapt to predation risks at an earlier detection stage of the predation sequence, as it allows substantial selective advantages for prey (3). Crickets have developed sensory mechanisms that allow them to detect predation at earlier times and successfully avoid them (10). For example, crickets have long hairs at the end of the abdomen to detect movement, they use their strong legs to hop away from danger, and some can use camouflage to blend with their surroundings. So, this brings up the question “does jump performance vary with age/size?”

Size influences basically everything about biology (5). For many species, body size is largely a function of age. Younger individuals are similar in shape to adults, but increase in body size as they grow. As the individuals grow, however, they also gain more experience performing different movements. This practice could lead to improved performance, more consistent performance, or both. The more body mass an organism has, the more muscles they have as well, which could potentially increase their ability to jump higher than organisms with lower body mass. In addition, the length of an organism could also influence how high an organism can jump. If an organism is longer in length, they may have an advantage in jumping higher than organisms who are shorter in length. For example, longer legs can result in higher jumps because

as mass increases, insects will have a greater amount of available energy and a larger opposing inertia, resulting in higher take-off velocities (12).

However, this scaling of jump performance is largely determined by the relative scaling of body mass and muscle mass. Consider the fact that a human is 163 million times larger than a flea, yet can only jump about three times higher. Although it may seem counterintuitive, the relationship between the energy required to jump and the energy available to power a jump predicts similar jumping ability for animals of different sizes.

Energy required to jump to a certain height (EP):

$$E = \text{body mass } (m_b) \times \text{gravitational acceleration } (g) \times \text{height } (h)$$

Energy available from muscle to power a jump (EM)

$$EM = \text{energy density of muscle } (e) \times \text{muscle mass } (m_M)$$

Solving for h :

$$h = emM / gmB$$

Assuming that g and e are constant, h depends only on the proportion of body mass to muscle mass. Referring back to the human and flea example, there are very different body plans and different proportions of muscle that contribute to their jump, so it is not surprising to see at least some difference in jumping ability. But species that are more closely related, or individuals of the same species, would be expected to have similar shape and muscle proportions despite differences in overall size. Thus, animals of similar shapes are expected to jump around the same height regardless of their differences in size (1).

Again, however, the assumptions of this simplification may not hold true for all organisms. There are several factors that may be contributing to the different trends that are seen in organisms' jump performances. On one end, there is an evolutionary perspective that argues younger organisms have higher jump performance since these juveniles are more likely to survive and successfully escape predation. On the other end, there are other factors that may come into play, such as age, experience, and learning, that argues older organisms have higher jump performance due to having more time and experience spent into learning how to effectively use their jumping mechanisms. Many studies have found that as animals get larger, jump performance levels increase or remain constant (7). Other previous studies have found that as animals get larger, jump performance levels decrease (5). Thus, the relationship between jump performance and body size of organisms remains controversial.

Based on these concepts, we hypothesize that similarly shaped animals could achieve the same jump performance at any body size, but older animals have jump performance that is both greater and more consistent due to their greater experience. Thus, we predict that jump performance will be higher in larger, older animals and the variation within an individual will be lower for larger, older animals.

House crickets (*Acheta domesticus*) are a great model system for exploring the effects of body size on jump performance. They have a specific development where they increase in size as they get older, yet remain similar shape as they age. Due to their similar shape across different ages, it is expected that the younger and older crickets should jump about the same height despite their differences in size, since jump performance is independent of body mass (see above). They are also known to be great jumpers, which is important since it is one of their main escape methods from predators. According to Darwin's theory of natural selection, it is expected that

natural selection will act much stronger on crickets who are not as great at jumping. Therefore, crickets who are strong jumpers are more likely to escape danger and survive, increasing their fitness levels.

Previous studies in crickets found decreasing jump distance with age, but jump distance is not a great measurement of performance. Being able to jump the furthest may not always be considered the “best” method, especially when trying to escape a predator. For example, crickets may try to look for a safe place to hide from a predator, which may not always be the furthest distance from where they are at. In addition, crickets may be able to jump far distances, but they may not be great at controlling their jump, resulting in less accuracy and consistency within their jumps. Therefore, it would be a better measurement to determine the velocity of their jump, since jump height and jump distance can be calculated from velocity using ballistic/projectile equations.

There is evidence that crickets use elastic energy to power their jumps. Crickets are cold-blooded organisms, meaning that their muscle performance is highly dependent on temperature. In a study conducted by Deban and Anderson, they found that house crickets jumped with greater performance than would be possible using direct muscle shortening. They also found that their jump performance declined at the lowest temperature, yet jump power still exceeded available muscle power. These results supported the idea that crickets use an elastic-recoil mechanism that enhances their jump performance (3). Another study found that jumping insects store energy in elastic structures, such as springs, and then rapidly release it using latches (6). This conversion of elastic to kinetic energy drives the movement in crickets, allowing them to jump 50-60 times their body length (6). Thus, elastic energy is a crucial concept that allows crickets, as well as other small animals, to be great jumpers. Animals that use

elastic energy are more likely to fit the universal jumping performance argument, which argues that jump performance is independent of body mass, resulting in a constant jump height regardless of the insect's body size (5).

Methods

We measured the jump performance from five 2-week-old crickets (mass = 0.0265-0.0303 g) and five 5-week-old crickets (mass = 0.4758-0.264 g) using high-speed videography. First, the crickets were placed in a narrow acrylic box (3x20x10 cm) with a cardboard ramp protruding from the open top at an angle of about 45 degrees and were encouraged to jump using light taps with a paint brush. 10 jumps of five 2-week-old crickets were collected using a high-speed camera, with a total of 50 jumps collected. Afterward, the body mass was measured for each of the crickets in this age group. This process was then repeated with five 5-week-old crickets for a grand total of 100 jumps collected. The videos were digitized using DLTdv8 by tracking the 2D position of the cricket's eye through time. Then, the position data were analyzed using a bespoke MATLAB script which first smoothed the data using a 4th order Butterworth filter to eliminate any noise from the video tracking, then calculated the 2D velocity as the first derivative of position; the maximum velocity was recorded as the value of jump velocity for each trial. Finally, a Barlett's test was used to test the null hypothesis that variances were equal across all individuals.

Results

On average, older crickets tended to have greater jump velocity than younger crickets, but there were no significant differences in the variance in jump velocities between individuals ($p = 0.0502$) or between the age classes ($p = 0.0604$, Fig. 1).

Fig 1. Box-plots of jump velocity by individual (left) and age class (right). There were no significant differences in the variances between individuals ($p = 0.0502$) or age classes ($p = 0.0604$).

There was a significant difference in maximum jump performance with performance being significantly higher at larger body sizes (red, $p = 0.03$, Fig. 2). However, overall jump performance was not significantly predicted by individual ($p = 0.068$), but was significantly higher for larger crickets (blue, $p = 0.006$, Fig. 2).

Fig 2. Maximum jump performance was significantly higher at larger body sizes (red, $p = 0.03$). Overall jump performance was not significantly predicted by individual ($p = 0.068$), but was significantly higher for larger crickets (blue, $p < 0.006$). Dashed lines represent scaling proportional to body length ($b = \frac{1}{3}$) or body mass ($b = 1$).

Discussion

Our findings were consistent with our hypothesis. Larger, older crickets do have a greater jump performance than smaller, younger crickets. However, the slope of this relationship is much less than what is predicted based on body length or body mass, suggesting that the effect of size/age on jump performance is not reflective of a fundamentally different scaling law from the relationship between body mass and energy density of muscle. On the other hand, our results do not agree with the hypothesis that larger, older crickets have more consistent jump performance than smaller, younger crickets. Thus, experience may not fully explain the greater jump performance of larger, older crickets.

Since jumping is used as an escape method, older crickets may represent the individuals that were better able to survive from dangerous situations throughout their life. In other words, these results may be reflecting natural selection in action. This could potentially be a reason why we see the pattern of larger, older crickets having a higher average jump velocity compared to smaller, younger crickets. Also, jumping may not necessarily be the most prominent anti-predatory mechanism in younger crickets. Because of their size, they can easily hide from predators and avoid being eaten, which may explain a lower average jump velocity compared to the older crickets (2). In other words, since jumping is energy costly, younger crickets turn to a different method to avoid predators, such as hiding, since it does not require as much energy. Larger crickets, however, are not able to hide as easily from predators since they are much larger than the younger crickets (2), so natural selection is much stronger on older crickets who have higher jump velocity to successfully escape predators.

Previous experiments suggest that crickets jump using stored elastic energy (3). When thinking about elastic energy, one can picture what happens to a rubber band when you sling it backwards and then let go. The recoiling effect of the rubber band after it has been pulled back then let go represents a form of elastic energy. Crickets are also known as ectotherms, meaning that they have a body temperature matching the ambient temperature of their environment. When crickets are placed in a cold environment, it is expected to see a lower jump performance since their muscles do not function as well in the cold (6). On the other hand, when they are placed in an environment at their optimal temperature, it is expected to see a higher jump performance since their muscles work much better. However, elastic energy is significant because this is not temperature-dependent. Therefore, this type of mechanism can help animals get the most energy possible out of their muscles when jumping (6, 12). Older crickets could either have a different

proportion of muscle mass that contributes to jumping or could take greater advantage of stored elastic energy compared with younger crickets. A direct measurement of the leg muscles could help reveal the source of these differences.

Despite one of our hypotheses being supported, there were some possible errors throughout this experiment. For one, we motivated the crickets using a paint brush to simulate a potential source of danger and cause the crickets to jump. However, throughout the trials the crickets may have realized that the repetitive stimulus was not dangerous, potentially affecting the quality of their jumps during later trials. Additionally, there may not have been a long enough rest period for some crickets in between each trial, which could have decreased their jump performance due to fatigue. Some of the jumps were also not completely parallel to the camera resulting in potential underestimates of velocity measurements in 2D. For future studies, a larger sample size may increase the reliability of the study, as well as using other organisms that also use a spring-like mechanism to jump. It would also be important to ensure that enough rest periods are provided for the crickets in between each jump trial. Lastly, the use of two cameras for 3D analysis will allow more accurate and precise velocity readings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, smaller crickets have higher jump performance that is similar to that of larger animals, consistent predictions from the energetics of jumping, but jump performance is not completely independent of size. Similar variance at different sizes suggests that this pattern may not be explained by differences in experience that fine-tune the jump. Future studies are needed to identify additional morphological or physiological factors that could explain the greater performance of larger individuals.

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